

PROBLEMS OF THE NEED FOR JUSTIFICATION OF ENTERPRISE'S FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC STABILITY

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IJEFI

SJIF 2024: 3.057

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Received: November 10, 2023

Revised: November 15, 2023

Accepted: November 24, 2023

Published: December 29, 2023

Funding source for publication:

Samarkand branch of Tashkent state
University of Economics

Abstract. The paper is devoted to the conditions for ensuring the stability of the formation of financial resources of an enterprise, including in conditions of crisis. These phenomena are characterized by shortages of financial resources, which influences both directly the financial decisions of enterprises and its partnership with other economic entities, and hence the further growth of its assets and the extensiveness and intensity of development of activities. Particular attention is paid to measures for the financial recovery of enterprises.

Key words: economic growth, financial resources, financial transactions, financial recovery, efficiency

INTRODUCTION

The financial condition of the enterprise has always been given special attention, since it determines not only the successful operation of the enterprise and the increase in the property of the owners, but also the possibility of cooperation with partners, international organizations, obtaining financing, credit resources, the formation and development of further cooperation with major partners who can take an interest in the overall successes and current position of the enterprise not only in the market, but also in general, from the point of view of sustainability in general.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Issues of the sustainability of the financial condition of an enterprise have always been the subject of close attention of both scientists and practitioners. Thus, the following works were devoted to the study of the financial condition of the enterprise Bayetdinov M. [4], who believes that ensuring the liquidity of business entities is a necessary condition for the expansion, technical and technological re-equipment of their production, Zainalov Zh.R., Akhrorov Z.O.[11], who devoted research to the impact of taxes on the financial stability of enterprises Astanakulov O.T. [2], whose research is devoted to the study of the conditions for the financial stability of an enterprise in order to ensure opportunities for its investment activities, Kotane, I., & Kuzmina-Merlino, I, who came to the opinion that a comprehensive analysis of business performance is necessary [7]. And Dennis, and Tu (2007) [10], Rivenbark, Roenigk, and Allison (2010) [8], and Johnson, Kioko, and Hildreth (2012) [6], in accordance with the concept they developed, grouped financial indicators into six categories . Financial ratios are widely used in local governments, as evidenced by the 42 financial ratios proposed by the International City or County Management Association [5]. Believes that financial indicators can serve as a means of increasing the organizational potential of life support organizations [9].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the process of working on the study, the authors based on current trends, legislative and regulatory support, development of the county's education policies, approved by legislative and regulatory acts, used a systematic approach and scientific analyses.

ANALYSES AND RESULTS

A stable source of formation of financial resources of enterprises depends on their propensity for one or another type of activity. Consequently, the mechanism for the formation and distribution of income and all other forms of financial relations must operate in conjunction with financial policy (at the level of enterprises, regions, state) on the basis of legal, regulatory requirements and all other components of the financial system.

The formation and distribution of enterprise income is not isolated from the problems of financial and economic stability of enterprises in modern conditions of economic development.

In modern conditions, the problem of having a sufficient level of funds to carry out activities in the field of ensuring financial stability and maintaining high solvency of enterprises becomes more complex. The basis for an objective understanding of the functioning mechanism of a given enterprise and strengthening its financial and economic stability can be created by conditions for the effective distribution and conduct of financial transactions.

In the current conditions, distribution and financial operations, which describe individual aspects of the financial and economic situation of an enterprise, are inextricably linked with each other, and their relationship should be the subject of ensuring the stability of their development [2].

The methodological approach to ensuring the financial stability of an enterprise firmly links its own property with borrowed property, financial with non-financial, in monetary form with non-monetary one. In this case, the starting point for ensuring stability should be one's own resources in cash and compliance with the conditions of financial balance, as the starting point for strengthening the financial position of the enterprise. Therefore, a specific value should be to ensure the growth rate of enterprise performance [1]. But here the priority should be compliance with the established proportions and rates of development. Violation of the existing proportions can lead to a deterioration in the financial condition of enterprises, an increase in tension, a lack of own sources, which will lead not only to tension in all financial relations of enterprises, in increasing their efficiency, but also in the importance of finance as a powerful lever in achieving stability of development and strengthening their financial potential.

Therefore, strengthening the role of measures aimed at preventing the negative consequences of enterprise development will lead to increased efficiency of enterprises, strengthening financial potential and achieving their goals.

In the context of the revival of New Uzbekistan, the financial activities of

enterprises should be more efficient and strong. The greater the organization of financial relations at each stage of the historical development of enterprises and the stronger the financial potential of enterprises, the more effectively it is consistent with other economic instruments and used in accordance with the requirements of the objective economic requirements of the market.

Enterprises adapted differently to the conditions and consequences of the crisis. Crisis conditions initially reduce the volume of economic activity, making it impossible to quickly find a place in both the domestic and foreign markets and successfully compete with other entities. Many, finding themselves in a crisis situation, cannot overcome it and need government financial support (tax breaks, subsidies).

The purpose of this study is to identify the causes of loss of income (profit) of enterprises in times of crisis and to develop measures to overcome the decline in activity volumes and ensure profitability of work.

To analyze the reasons for the loss of income (profit), it is necessary to give a general description of the state of the financial and economic activities of enterprises under the current conditions of quarantine (from March 16, 2022 to November 2022) before its easing (January 2023). During this period, there was a decline in production (sales of goods and services) of up to 40%; tax revenues in budget revenues of all levels decreased to 20% due to the narrowing of the tax base and the introduction of tax breaks and subsidies for service sector enterprises.

In addition, the reason for the unprofitability of individual enterprises that did not cease their activities during quarantine lay in insufficiently effective management of financial resources.

When analyzing the activities of all enterprises, it is necessary to note the general shortcomings inherent in the organization of finance.

Given the acute lack of equity capital, enterprises do not effectively use such a method of replenishing financial resources as attracting funds from the population. But, at the same time, experience shows that attracting funds from the population is the most effective source of working capital, compared to other types of credit resources, until the enterprise is fully provided with its own funds. But this source will actually operate when the enterprise fulfills its obligations to the population, that is, to investors.

Thus, the cornerstone of the financial activities of enterprises is the participation in it of a significant part of the legal entities and individuals served. They, with their funds, participate in the formation of sources of their own working

capital necessary for the implementation of their economic activities. The degree of their participation in the formation of financial resources of enterprises determines the degree of their interest in the results of the enterprises' activities. Therefore, the level of accumulation of enterprises to a large extent determines their financial potential.

In times of crisis, having reduced the number of clients, many enterprises, in particular those in the service sector, undermined their own base, losing guaranteed buyers, the main buyers of their products. The reduction in the number of consumers also affected the prestige of enterprises.

It is necessary to work to restore the number of consumers, provide them with benefits, and practice tax payments.

In our opinion, at this time the role of service consumers as the main clients is underestimated. Which leads to a violation of one of the basic principles - the economic participation of clients in the life of enterprises.

The experience of enterprises shows that the refusal of clients to participate economically in the activities of enterprises leads to the cessation of their existence for reasons caused by the crisis.

A distinctive feature of manufacturing enterprises that sets them apart from other types of service enterprises is the formation of capital and its control. Unlike business enterprises, the amount of total capital is not constant and depends on the financial potential of the enterprises. When the founder leaves the enterprise, he takes his share of the funds, thereby reducing the total capital and, accordingly, the financial potential. Therefore, to increase stability, part of the profit is formed by a fund, which serves as a kind of financial reserve.

The factor sufficient for the successful application of this principle - the volume (at the stage of enterprise development) and the quality of economic participation - ensures the achievement of the enterprise's goal, that is, the satisfaction of needs. But modern reality shows the opposite, when assessing the stability of enterprises according to this criterion, only their existence is ensured, but not the achievement of its goals. And, as a consequence, if an enterprise remains in this state for a sufficiently long time, its founders, not receiving benefits from their activities, leave the enterprise, further exacerbating its financial potential. Having lost its financial base, the enterprise will be forced to cease to exist.

At this time, the founding fund practically does not participate in the formation of equity capital. The share of the founding fund mainly belongs to the founders, and no measures are taken to revive the economic interest of enterprises in the final

results of enterprises. And this is the main reason for the passivity of the founders. If the founders of enterprises are not provided with certain benefits, he does not care who manages this enterprise and how, what is its economic condition or financial potential.

It is recommended that each enterprise develop a program for reviving the economic participation of the founders of the authorized capital; it is necessary to provide for the possibility of increasing the authorized capital, attracting deposits from the population, and increasing its number. But the main form of financial support for enterprises is participation in the sale of products (goods) as buyers, in providing the enterprise with guaranteed sales of products (goods), but this should be encouraged in various forms.

Foreign experience shows that bonuses to the founders of the authorized capital of enterprises for the sale of products (goods) or the purchase of raw materials are beneficial even in conditions of unprofitable activities, since this stimulates consumer demand and very quickly leads to break-even, and then profitable activity. In addition, for enterprises, there is an urgent need for social management as a special function of enterprises. There is experience:

- ❖ social management, but it is scattered, the forecasts of social development that are compiled provide, firstly, for the social development of production participants, not buyers;
- ❖ secondly, they will not be supported by material resources;
- ❖ thirdly, they are administrative in nature.

These plans are not linked to activities, are not focused on workers, and control over the implementation of social programs is characterized by formalism.

Social management acquires paramount importance only if the goal is to preserve the enterprise it should focus on satisfying the interests of workers, increasing their standard of living and social protection.

Another important factor is that during periods of crisis, the income of enterprises decreases, since many enterprises continue to reduce the volume of economic activity in all industries. Thus, as of January 1, 2023, the volume of sales of enterprise products decreased by 12%, the turnover of food enterprises - by 40%, the volume of production of essential goods - by 24%. This was a consequence of the fact that in such conditions the volumes that were capable of ensuring profitable (profitable) economic activity were not calculated.

A decrease in the quality of control over compliance with settlement and payment discipline can lead to an increase in accounts payable, which in some cases

exceeds accounts receivable, and sometimes the volume of activity. Losses are largely determined not by the amount of debt itself, but by its structure. The presence of receivables in sufficiently large volumes is a direct diversion of financial resources, which, given the existing lack of own working capital, significantly reduced the efficiency of economic and financial activities.

CONCLUSION

An analysis of individual indicators of the financial activities of enterprises showed problems common to all, such as a significant share of additional capital. The growth of this indicator occurred as a result of revaluations of fixed assets, in which group average conversion factors were used, which led to an increase in value, and subsequently to a distortion of the financial condition and an increase in the tax base.

In order to find ways to financially improve enterprises, it is necessary to use all the best that came before, and this is:

- control over the correct expenditure of financial resources and the safety of enterprise property;
- preservation of all sectors of activity with subsequent diversification: territorial - strengthening its influence in cities; sectoral – agriculture, flour milling, fish processing, road cleaning, pharmacies, household and industrial services;
- selection of production as a priority activity for enterprises that provides income (commodity resources, jobs and employee income).

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